

THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PREDICTION OF LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Simple supported or clamped rectangular composite plates were analysed for static equivalent impact load. Using this analysis method we could obtain the equivalent impact load and impact damage condition in composite laminates. The main analysis was based on the conservation of energy principle. The deduction of element stiffness matrix was based on the total potential energy principle. A step-by-step incremental transverse displacement procedure was used to calculate plate load and ply stresses. The ply failure region was calculated using the Tsai-Wu criterion and the corresponding failure modes were determined using the maximum stress criteria. Reduced elastic moduli were then used in the failure region in subsequent incremental transverse displacements of analysis. In tests, we saw the low-velocity impact damage appearance of laminates. The interior damage condition was determined by "holographic non-destructive testing". The "holographic nondestructive testing" could easily determine the damage sites and damage areas of laminates. The theoretical values of equivalent impact loads P and impact damage areas showed good agreement with their experiment values.

INTRODUCTION

The wide use of advanced composite materials and the rapid increase in their fields of application have necessitated a better understanding of the performance of composites. Although fiber composites have a high strength-to-weight ratio, they are much more brittle than most metals. Therefore, they are easily damaged by impact, especially those perpendicular to the laminate plane. Even low-velocity impacts from dropped tools can cause substantial damage. Often, the residual strength can be significantly reduced by impacts that leave no visible damage.

Most low-velocity impact problems can be treated as quasi-static problems. Because the impact duration is much longer than the time required by the propagating waves to travel from the impact site to the supports or free edges. Furthermore, studies have shown that impact tests and equivalent static tests produce essentially the same damage in thin composite laminates. Therefore, the analysis presented here will assume slow transverse loading.

The purpose of this article is to develop a new kind of theoretical and experimental prediction method of low-velocity impact damage in composite laminates. The theoretical method is based on the conservation of energy principle. It is a statement that the energy of the system before impact is equal to the total energy at any time thereafter. The conservation of energy can be expressed as follows:

$$U_B(t) + U_S(t) + U_p(t) + U_k(t) = U_p(0) + U_k(0)$$

Where $U_B(t)$ represents the bending energy of the panel at any time, t . Similarly, $U_s(t)$ represents the stretching energy and $U_p(t)$ and $U_k(t)$ are respectively the potential and kinetic energies of the system at any time, t . The terms $U_p(0)$ and $U_k(0)$ are the kinetic and potential energies of the system just prior to impact at the time $t=0$.

Then, we can use finite element method to calculate the most critical loading state -- the largest displacement state -- the state when the velocity of impactor is zero. Next, the most critical ply stresses in each element are calculated and plate is judged for failure using the Tsai-Wu and maximum stress criteria. The analysis is continued for additional increments of displacements using reduced moduli in failed elements. Using this method we can get not only the impact areas but also the damage modes.

ANALYSIS

The laminates discussed here are shown in Fig.1. One layer of the laminates and the element division of the layer in Fig.2. One element of the laminates in Fig.3. The fiber orientation in any layer is represented by an angle θ , measured from the X axis as shown in the figure. In the thickness direction, each ply is represented by one element. A typical element (see shade region) is defined by X,Y coordinates and thickness coordinate, Z.

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig.3

1. The Main Deformation of Element

The element in Fig.4 is a very small plate of one layer. Z_0 is the distance between the middle surface of the laminate and the middle surface of the element. So, from this figure we can see that although the middle surface of the laminate is in pure deflection state, the middle surface of the element will have a large in-plane deformation $u_0(x,y)$, $v_0(x,y)$. Because we consider the loads perpendicular to the element plane, we must consider the deflection of the element. The deformation of the element can be expressed as follows:

$$u(x,y,z) = u_0(x,y) - z \cdot \partial w / \partial x$$

$$v(x,y,z) = v_0(x,y) - z \cdot \partial w / \partial y$$

$$w(x,y,z) = w(x,y)$$

Fig.4

Where u, v and w are the element displacements in x, y and z directions, respectively. u_0 and v_0 are the element middle surface displacements in x and y directions, respectively. And from Strain-Displacement equations we can get:

$$\{\epsilon\} = \{\epsilon_0\} + z\{\psi\}$$

$$\{\epsilon_0\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \partial u_0 / \partial x \\ \partial v_0 / \partial y \\ \partial u_0 / \partial y + \partial v_0 / \partial x \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$\{\psi\} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\partial^2 w / \partial x^2 \\ -\partial^2 w / \partial y^2 \\ -2 \cdot \partial^2 w / \partial x \partial y \end{Bmatrix}$$

2. Equilibrium Equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 U^e &= \int_V \{\varepsilon\}^T \{\sigma\} dV \\
 &= \int_V \{ \{\varepsilon_0\} + z \{\psi\} \}^T [\bar{Q}] \{ \{\varepsilon_0\} \\
 &\quad + z \{\psi\} \} dV \\
 &= (t^3/12) \int_S \{\psi\}^T [\bar{Q}] \{\psi\} dx dy + t \int_S \{\varepsilon_0\}^T [\bar{Q}] \{\varepsilon_0\} dx dy
 \end{aligned}$$

The first term in the right side of the above equation is deflection strain energy, the second is in-plane deformation strain energy of the element.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{v}^e &= (\{\delta\}^e)^T \{\mathbf{F}\}^e = -(\delta_i^T, \delta_j^T, \delta_m^T, \delta_p^T) \cdot \{F_i, F_j, F_m, F_p\}^T \\
 \{\delta_i\}^T &= \{u_0, v_0, w, \theta_x, \theta_y\} \\
 \{F_i\} &= \{N_x, N_y, N_z, M_{\theta_x}, M_{\theta_y}\}^T
 \end{aligned}$$

Because the deflection strain energy and the in-plane deformation strain energy of the element are not coupled, the deflection and in-plane deformation can be considered alone. We change δ , F into the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \{\delta\}^T &= \{u_{0i}, \dots, v_{0p}, w_i, \dots, \theta_{xp}, \theta_{yp}\} 1 \times 20 \\
 \{F\}^T &= \{N_{xi}, \dots, N_{yp}, N_{zi}, M_{\theta_{xi}}, M_{\theta_{yi}}, \dots, M_{\theta_{yp}}\} 1 \times 20
 \end{aligned}$$

According to "the total potential energy principle":

$$\partial \pi^e / \partial \{\delta\}^e = 0, \quad \text{We obtain:}$$

$$\text{where: } \pi^e = U^e + V^e$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} [K_1]_{8 \times 8} & 0 \\ 0 & [K_2]_{12 \times 12} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_0 \\ v_0 \end{Bmatrix}_{8 \times 1} \\ \begin{Bmatrix} w \\ \theta_x \\ \theta_y \end{Bmatrix}_{12 \times 1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \end{Bmatrix}_{8 \times 1} \\ \begin{Bmatrix} N_z \\ M_{\theta_x} \\ M_{\theta_y} \end{Bmatrix}_{12 \times 1} \end{pmatrix}$$

In the above equation, $[K_1]$ is the stiffness matrix when the element is subjected to in-plane loads. $[K_2]$ is the stiffness matrix when the element is subjected to deflecting loads.

3. The Deduction of $[K_1]$, $[K_2]$:

When the element is only subjected to in-plane loads, we can deduce $[K_1]$ as follows:

$$[K_1]_{8 \times 8} = \int_V [B_1]^T [D] [B_1] dV$$

we take the shape functions of the element to be the normal shape functions of rectangle element (Ref.3). And from the above equation, we can obtain:

$$K_{11}^{(1)} = (t/6ab) \{ 2\bar{Q}_{11}b^2 + 3\bar{Q}_{16}ab + 2\bar{Q}_{66}a^2 \}$$

When the element is only subjected to deflecting loads, $[K_2]$ can be deduced as following:

$$[K_2]_{12 \times 12} = \int_V [B_2]^T [\bar{Q}] [B_2] dV$$

We take the shape functions of the element to be the normal shape functions of rectangle element (Ref.3). And from the above equation, we can

obtain:

$$K_{12,12}^{(2)} = \frac{t^3}{180ab} (20\bar{Q}_{11}b^2 - 15\bar{Q}_{16}ab + 8\bar{Q}_{66}a^2)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Impact Load

The laminate is made of T300/5208 graphite/epoxy with a quasi-isotropic layup (0,+60,-60), 12 layers, simple supported.

Table 1 Elastic properties of plate (kg/mm²)

E ₁	E ₂	ν ₁₂	G ₁₂	t(mm)
9000	800	0.32	460	0.14224

Fig.6

Fig.7

From Fig.7, we can see that theoretical values are somewhat bigger than experimental values. This is because that supports must have absorbed some energy in tests. While in theoretical calculating, it isn't considered.

2. Impact Damage

The plate is made of T300/5208 graphite/epoxy with a layup (0₂/90₂/0₂/90)_s, simple supported. Impact energy is 4.07 N.M. The elastic properties of one layer are listed in Table 1. The lamina strengths are listed in Table 2.

Table 2 Lamina strengths (kg/mm²)

X _t	X _c	S ₁₂	γ _t	Y _c
110	-84	6.7	3.2	-13

Fig.8 Damage in one layer

Table 3 Theoretical damage areas (cm²)

Layer	first	second	third	4th	5th	6th	7th	8th	9th	10	11	12
Damage	1.9	1.9	1.3	1.3	1.9	1.9	1.3	1.3	1.9	1.9	1.3	1.3

13	14	average
1.9	1.9	1.6

Experimental damage area is 1.4 cm^2 . From Table 3, we can see that the theoretical values show good agreement with their experimental values.

3. The Advantage of This Method

A. Using this method, we only need the material parameters of layer, elastic properties E_1 , E_2 , ν_{12} , G_{12} , fiber orientation θ , strengths X_t , X_c , Y_t , Y_c , S_{12} and thickness t . We can get the impact loads, impact damages under any impact energy. While these material constants of widely used lamina can be easily obtained.

B. Using this method, we can analyse not only laminates made of the same laminas but also hybrid laminates. Because one ply's elastic properties, fiber orientation, strengths are not related to that of other ply.

C. Using this method, we can analyse residual strength of laminates. Because we consider not only deflecting loads but also in-plane loads in our analysis.

D. Using this method, the impact site of the plate can be at any point. It needn't to be limited at the center of the plate.

4. The Disadvantage of This Method

A. In the analysis, we consider the composite materials as linear elastic. This cannot be very suitable.

B. In the analysis we do not consider the energy absorbed by supports, so the theoretical values are somewhat larger than corresponding experimental values.

C. In the analysis, we select the element to be non-coordinative when the element is only subjected to deflecting loads. The angles between two elements are non-coordinative.

D. In the analysis, we do not consider the energy dissipated by element damages.

TEST

1. Dropped Weight Impact

The impact conditions were selected to simulate energy from small rock damage to dropped tools. A typical laminated plate test specimen is shown in Fig.10. The plate is four edges clamped. The specimen is 7.6 cm by 22.9 cm. We select impact energy to be 14.7N.M. It is to simulate that a tool is dropped to an aircraft wing. The impactor is a steel stick with a hemispherical head, 2.54cm in diameter. It weighs 0.5225 kg.

Fig.9

Fig.10

Impactor

2. Impact Damage Appearance

The appearance of damage in graphite-epoxy plate specimens is shown in Fig.11 and Fig.12. The visible evidence of impact damage is a delamination on the back surface of the specimen as shown in Fig.12. The front surface of the specimen has no visible damage. The contact region between impactor and plate is shown in Fig.11.

Fig.11 Front surface

Fig.12 Back surface

3. Interior Damage

The specimen interior damage is examined with the "holographic nondestructive testing". The edges of the specimen examined are clamped. In order to get the interior damage condition of laminates, we can heat the specimen on its back surface, and from its front surface we take photographs.

Fig.13 Typical hologram of specimen before impact, without damage detected.

Fig.14 Typical hologram of specimen after impact. One damage at the impact site.

CONCLUSIONS

Simple supported or clamped rectangle composite plates were analysed for static equivalent impact load. Using this analysis method we could obtain the equivalent impact load and impact damage condition in composite laminates. The main analysis was based on the conservation of energy principle. The deduction of element stiffness matrix was based on the total potential energy principle. A step-by-step incremental transverse displacement procedure was used to calculate plate load and ply stresses. The ply failure region was calculated using the Tsai-Wu criterion and the corresponding failure modes were determined using the maximum stress criteria. Reduced elastic moduli were then used in the failed region in subsequent incremental transverse displacements of analysis. The analysis predicted that the failure would initiate as splitting in the bottom-most ply and then progress to other plies. The size and shape of the ply damage regions were different for different plies. The splitting damage region in each ply was elongated in its fiber direction. The theoretical method can not only determine the impact loads and impact damage areas, it can determine the residual strength of laminates as well. In tests, we saw the low-velocity impact damage appearance of laminates. The interior damage condition could be determined by "holographic nondestructive testing". The "holographic nondestructive testing" used in this paper could easily determine the damage sites and areas of laminates. The theoretical values of equivalent impact loads P and impact damage areas showed good agreement with their experimental values.

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